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Endocrine Disruption and the Future of Animal Testing: A Legal Analysis of EU Regulatory Barriers in Balancing Animal Welfare, Public Health, and the Internal Market

Ton van den Brink¹

1. Introduction

This report aims to identify the legal barriers to the transition toward non-animal testing in the assessment of chemical toxicity within the European Union, with particular attention to substances with endocrine-disrupting properties. To this end, it undertakes a comprehensive analysis of EU law, ranging from the foundational Treaties—which already enshrine binding obligations concerning, *inter alia*, animal welfare and public health protection—to the relevant secondary legislation. This is further complemented by an examination of the role and impact of EU executive acts and the activities of Union agencies. Substantively, the legal framework is assessed through the lens of a triadic balancing of public interests: (1) the interest in animal welfare, which ultimately supports the abolition of all animal testing; (2) the public health interest, which necessitates protecting individuals from exposure to endocrine-disrupting substances; and (3) the internal market interest, which aims to safeguard the free movement of chemicals and ensure undistorted market access within the Union. The analysis proceeds from the assumption that the current legislative framework is designed to reconcile these three competing objectives.

¹ Ton van den Brink is full professor of EU Legislative Studies at Utrecht University. He wishes to thank Yunus Oppier and Ella Ramondt for their invaluable contributions to this report and earlier versions thereof.

2. An overview of the legal framework

The EU legislative framework relevant to facilitating the use of animal-free methods for the identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals is strongly diversified.

Figure 1. Hierarchy of norm-setting in EU law. The figure excludes the role of the European Court of Justice in norm-setting as well as national norm-setting.

This reflects in part the multi-level structure of the EU and its so-called hierarchy of norms.

The EU hierarchy of norms refers to how legal norms interrelate in the EU and which authority they possess. The system distinguishes various levels of norm-setting, as displayed in the figure above, the level of (1) the **EU treaties**; (2) the level of **EU legislation**; (3) **executive rule making** by the Commission or the Council; and lastly (4) **rule-making by EU agencies**. Before elaborating those levels more in detail, I will use an example to show how this system affects the decision-making on chemical substances.

A good example of a situation in which all these levels are relevant concerns the decision-making on Bisphenol A. The EU Treaties (level 1) provide that the EU should strive for a high level of public health protection and that it should ensure the effective functioning of the internal market. To implement this ambition for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food, the EU legislature adopted a regulation in 2004 (level 2).² The Regulation establishes inter alia the general requirements; that the Commission may adopt ‘specific measures’ for certain groups of materials and articles; and that the European Food and Safety

² Regulation 1935/2004/EU.

Authority (EFSA) must be consulted on those specific measures and has a role in the assessment of substances. Based thereon, the Commission banned the use of Bisphenol A in food contact materials by means of an implementing regulation, one of the instruments of executive rule-making (level 3).³ As provided for by the legislative regulation, the Commission based itself on the risk assessment which the EFSA had made.⁴ This example thus shows the hierarchal relations between the various levels well.

The highest level is the *foundational or constitutional level*. **The EU Treaties** (the Treaty on the EU; the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU -TFEU; and the Charter on Fundamental Rights – CFR) form the core of this primary level. This level represents the apex of the hierarchy of norms. As a consequence, all other measures of the EU must comply with (and must be in line with) the norms of this level. The objectives of the Treaties and the way these are operationalized at this level thus form the logical starting point of the analysis. Importantly, this includes whether and to which extent the EU institutions may act at all in a particular field. An important issue indeed, as the EU functions on the basis of the principle of conferred powers (article 4 TEU) which means that the EU institutions can only make laws and take action in areas in which the EU Member States have explicitly agreed to give the EU the authority to do so at the Treaty level.

The second level is that of *EU legislation*. EU legislation is used here in a narrow sense. It comprises not of all legally binding norms, but only those that have been adopted by the EU's legislative institutions. These institutions (the Commission, the European Parliament and the Council) derive their power, and their responsibility, to act directly from the Treaties. Alignment with the Treaties is essential, as the Court of Justice may annul legislation otherwise. At the same time, the EU legislative procedure (article 289 TFEU) has a high level of legitimacy: the directly elected European Parliament has full legislative powers. Moreover, the involvement of the European Commission and the Council ensures that the general EU interest and national interests are represented in the decision-making as well. As such, the EU legislative procedure allows for elaborate consideration and balancing of – possibly conflicting – public interests such as those at issue. Legislation in the EU mostly comes in two forms: directives and regulations. There is no hierarchical difference between the two. Both are full-fledged legislative acts, but they differ in terms of their legal effects. Regulations are directly applicable but directives must first be transposed into national legislation. The choice between a regulation or a directive is mostly a discretionary choice of the EU legislature. Article 288 TFEU prescribes that a directive is only binding in relation to the 'results to be achieved' but leaves the Member States the freedom to select the appropriate 'forms and methods' to achieve those results. Directives are thereby often adopted when the EU legislature seeks to offer flexibility to the Member States. This is, however, not an absolute rule. Some directives leave very little discretionary room for the Member States whereas, oppositely, regulations may instead offer a far from comprehensive regulatory framework. In terms of legislative policy, we witness an

³ Implementing Regulation 2024/3190/EU.

⁴ European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), *Bisphenol A in food is health risk*, <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/bisphenol-food-health-risk>.

increasing popularity of regulations, for their ability to offer an uniformly applicable regulatory framework. This includes the replacement of directives by regulations in case of changes of existing regulatory frameworks. As we will see, this applies to the regulatory frameworks at issue in this report as well.

The third level of the EU's hierarchy of norms concerns the level of *executive rule-making*. These norms have a lower status in the hierarchy of norms as they are not adopted by the legislature but by executive institutions, most notably the Commission. Most of the norms the EU produces are actually not adopted by the EU legislature but rather by one of its executive institutions, the European Commission or the Council. The idea is that the 'regulatory state'⁵ of which the EU is an exponent requires and results in such a high level of regulatory density that the legislature simply lacks the capacity to regulate all aspects of an issue. The oftentimes highly technical nature of such aspects makes it, furthermore, even *unnecessary* for the legislature to make these decision themselves. Rather than a – political – balancing of possibly conflicting interests, such regulation requires the necessary *expertise* to make informed regulatory choices.

To this end, the EU legislature may empower the Commission or the Council to adopt so-called 'delegated' or 'implementing' acts within the sphere of the legislative act in question (or a part thereof). Apart from a high level of technical detail, the expectation that the regulatory framework will need frequent updates (e.g. in light of scientific advancements) may be another reason behind such empowerments. Executive rule-making is thereby not directly based on the Treaties but rather on a legislative act. Its position within the EU's hierarchy of norms is further manifested by the requirement that a rule-making act must not only comply with the Treaties, but equally with the EU legislative act on which it is based. This includes the empowerment clause (which may restrict and qualify the Commission's or Council's discretion) but all other provisions of the legislative act must be respected as well. A substance criterion for such executive rule-making is that it should remain limited to the so-called non-essential elements of an issue. The Court has further specified this to mean that *political choices which require conflicting interests at issue to be weighed* must in case remain in the legislative domain (and are thus off limits for the Commission individually).⁶

This lower level in the EU's hierarchy of norms comes with limited legitimacy. The European Parliament is not directly involved in the decision-making on these implementing and delegated acts and fewer procedural safeguards apply. In the case of implementing acts (article 291 TFEU) the committee procedure system applies, *comitology* in the EU jargon. This implies that the Commission needs to submit draft implementing acts to committees of national experts. This type of decision-making thus relies primarily on technical expertise rather than on democratic legitimacy. The legislation at issue contains several provisions on which such implementing acts can be based. The situation is somewhat different for delegated acts (art. 290 TFEU). National experts are involved in the adoption of these acts as well, but the political institutions (Council and European

⁵ G. Majone, 'The rise of the regulatory state in Europe', *West European Politics* 1994 (17) 3, pp. 77-101.

⁶ Case C-355/10 *Schengen Border Code*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:516.

Parliament) may block them and are thus more closely involved in the decision-making on these acts. In the literature, they are sometimes qualified as ‘quasi-legislation’. This type of decision-making has only been introduced with the Treaty of Lisbon (2009) which means it is only included in legislation adopted after that. The Biocides products regulation provides for example:

Article 28

Amendment of Annex I (list of authorized active substances)

1. The Commission shall be empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 83 amending Annex I, after receiving the opinion of the Agency, in order to include active substances provided that there is evidence that they do not give rise to concern according to paragraph 2 of this Article.

On the basis of this article the Commission has for instance decided that potassium sorbate could be authorized under the BPR.⁷

The fourth and final level relevant to this report pertains to *soft law* and decision-making by *EU agencies*. The European Commission and EU agencies can adopt soft law measures, which take various forms but share the characteristic of not being legally binding. A notable example are the numerous ECHA guidance documents addressing different aspects of REACH, based on technical and scientific input. These soft law measures aim to clarify and operationalize complex aspects of the Regulation, facilitating decision-making on registrations for both applicants and the authorities responsible for approval. While compliance with such guidance is often high, it is important to note that these guidances do not necessarily represent ‘the law’. Indeed, the Court may not always align with the interpretations of EU legislation presented by the authors of these soft law measures. Agencies (or the Commission for that matter) that adopt these guidances do not represent the legislative institutions, and can thus not be considered to voice the intention of the legislature. The Court may, therefore, diverge from these if it considers that the intentions of the legislature would require it to do so.

The role of EU agencies within the EU’s institutional framework warrants closer examination, as they can be involved in rule-making (either through the adoption of soft law or by preparing legally binding rules) and by concrete decision-making. With regard to the latter, the EU legislature has granted various agencies the authority to make concrete decisions for specific cases.⁸ However, the legislature may not freely delegate rule-making authority to agencies. This may already be deduced from the articles 290 and 291 TFEU which foresee only the Commission and the Council as the authors of these acts. The Court has ruled that the Treaties do not permit agencies to wield “broad discretionary powers”⁹

⁷ Delegated Regulation 2021/807/EU.

⁸ Which are then implementing acts on the basis of article 291 TFEU as these acts may entail both rule-making and single-case decision. By contrast, delegated acts may only encompass rule-making acts.

⁹ Case 9-56 *Meroni*, ECLI:EU:C:1958:7.

or to adopt acts "having the force of law."¹⁰ That said, the Court has subsequently qualified its former stricter approach and allowed limited rule-making authority for agencies, provided that the delegation is confined to "clearly defined executive powers".¹¹

In the context of the agencies discussed in this report, the limits on their authority have been reflected in a clear distinction between *risk assessment* and *risk management*. This distinction has been applied in a 1999 White Paper from the Commission. Risk assessment relates to the scientific evaluation of hazards and potential exposure associated with a chemical substance. It involves identifying and quantifying risks to human health and the environment. Risk management, however, implies "*political decision and involves judgements not only based on science but on a wider appreciation of the wishes and needs of society*".¹² As a result, agencies may not be entrusted with risk management responsibilities. This restriction is grounded not only in the constitutional limits established by the Court's case law and the Treaties but also in concerns about the potential for an "unwarranted dilution of democratic accountability." These considerations led the Commission to ensure that such tasks were to be excluded from EFSA's mandate (and this applies to ECHA as well).¹³

Agencies' involvement in rule-making can be divided between the adoption of soft law measures (explained above) and the preparation of rules that are eventually adopted by the Commission.¹⁴ In the latter case, agencies do not have formal decision-making authority. ECHA for instance has the power to make a recommendation to the Commission which substances from the Candidate List should be included in Annex XIV (the Authorization List).¹⁵ To this end, ECHA even needs to carry out public consultations and adjust its recommendation if necessary. This obviously gives the recommendation substantial weight, which, combined with the technical and scientific expertise of the agency, will make the Commission reluctant in diverging from these recommendations (even if it is formally allowed to diverge). Even though the agency does not possess any formal rule-making powers, its role in the decision-making may thus certainly be qualified as indirect, or quasi rule-making authority.

This report adopts the hierarchy of norms as its foundational structure, providing a clear and comprehensive overview of the key characteristics of each level and illustrating how the various elements of the legal framework interconnect. By emphasizing the broader framework, it ensures a holistic perspective, avoiding the pitfalls of narrowly focusing on individual legal measures and thereby neglecting their role within the overarching system. One final remark before starting the assessment of the various levels: the multileveled

¹⁰ Case 98-80 *Romano*, ECLI:EU:C:1981:104, See also: M. Chamon, 'EU Agencies between Meroni and Romano or the Devil and the Deep Blue Sea', *CMLRev* 2011 (48), pp. 1055-1075.

¹¹ Case C-270/12 *ESMA*, ECLI:EU:C:2014:18.

¹² Commission of the European Communities, *White Paper on Food Safety*, COM (1999) 719 final.

¹³ Agencies are primarily accountable, e.g. in terms of financial accountability, to the Commission. I will not address the bulk of literature on accountability of agencies here, see e.g. M. Scholten and A.F.M.

Brenninkmeijer (eds.), *Controlling EU agencies. The Rule of Law in a Multi-jurisdictional Legal Order*, Edward Elgar 2020; E. M. Busuioc, *European Agencies: Law and Practices of Accountability* OUP 2013.

¹⁴ E. Chiti, 'European Agencies' Rulemaking: Powers, Procedures and Assessment', *European Law Journal* 2013 (19) 1, pp. 93-110.

¹⁵ See article 58 of the REACH Regulation.

structure of the EU implies that the EU level is closely intertwined with national (and partly sub-national) levels of governance.¹⁶ Thus, decision-making processes at EU level may not be strictly separated from national levels and eventual regulatory frameworks can carry significant national dimensions as EU Member States may make their own choices in the implementation of EU legislation. However, this report focuses on the EU level only and thereby refrains from examining the aspects brought about by this multilevel structure.

3. Level 1: The EU Treaties

Three values, or policy objectives, are included in the TFEU which directly relate to the

move towards animal free methods for the identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals: Public health protection; animal protection and the internal market.

The **Internal market** has been a key ambition of the EU since the inception of the EU integration process. It is defined as ‘an area without internal frontiers in which the free movement of goods, persons, services and capital is ensured’.¹⁷ In the design of the internal market it has been acknowledged from the start that its well-functioning cannot rely on the abolition of trade obstacles such as import tariffs and quotas alone. Many of the practical obstacles to the free movement exist not as a result of national protectionist policies. Rather, they originate from diverging national legislations and practices which have been adopted to protect any possible public interest. As the Member States make different choices therein, free movement might be difficult. The cross-border trade in goods would, for instance, be confronted with obligations to comply with both home and host state regulations. To address this, the EU legislature has been empowered to adopt legislation *‘for the approximation of the provisions laid down by law, regulation or administrative action in Member*

¹⁶ Cf. L. F. M Besselink, *A Composite European Constitution*, Groningen: Europa Law Publishing 2007.

¹⁷ Article 26 TFEU.

States which have as their object the establishment and functioning of the internal market.¹⁸ Thus, the EU legislature has acquired a wide competence that ensures the objectives of the internal market (as its legislation applies to the whole of the EU and thus removes so-called distortions) and at the same time serves to protect other public interests that would otherwise be served by the Member States individually. In practice, we see the EU legislature indeed basing much legislation on article 114 TFEU, currently most notably to work on the EU's Green Deal. The EU legislature regularly faces criticism that it uses the internal market authorization to regulate in areas in which the internal market objectives actually seem marginal. The Court, however, has given much space to the legislature, provided that the internal market objectives are not completely absent.¹⁹ This allows the legislature to legislate in areas in which it lacks fewer or no specific authorizations. Public health is a competence that has largely remained in the hands of the Member States and animal welfare protection even fully. Through the broad interpretation of the internal market authorization, the EU is still able to legislate in these areas. Indeed, the threshold for such legislation, that it should contribute to the establishment and functioning of the internal market, is easily met for the assessment of health risks of substances that may be used in products that may be traded across the EU.

Public health protection has not been a key policy objective for the EU since the beginning of the EU integration process.²⁰ As EU cooperation focused rather on economic affairs, public health protection was considered a matter of national concern. When it became clear that public health could not just be separated from economic cooperation, a role for the EU gradually emerged in the field. The Treaty of Maastricht (1992) created a legal basis for the adoption of health policy measures, albeit a limited one (now article 168 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU). Moreover, public health protection has been added to the list to the so-called horizontal 'mainstreaming' provisions.²¹ These provisions require that the objectives of these policies must be considered across fields of EU legislation and policy to thus ensure consistency of EU policies. This strengthens the argument to use article 114 TFEU as a legal basis for public health inspired legislation. Indeed, it has been claimed, and perhaps rightly so, that *'other EU treaty bases that mention health as a policy objective (in consumer protection, labour law, and environment) have done more to promote and protect health than article 168, and many actions taken only under single market or other rules have contributed to health'* as well.²² Indeed, already in 1967 (long before the predecessor of now article 168 TFEU had been included in the Treaties) the Directive on the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances was adopted (which was replaced in 2008 by Regulation 1272/2008/EC).

¹⁸ Article 114 TFEU.

¹⁹ In the Tobacco advertisement decision: Case C-376/98 *Germany v. Parliament*, ECLI:EU:C:2000:544.

²⁰ For an account of the history of public health in the EU see: S.L. Greer and H. Jarman, 'What Is EU Public Health and Why? Explaining the Scope and Organization of Public Health in the European Union', *Journal of Health Politics, Policy and Law* 2021 (46) 1, pp. 23-47.

²¹ Article 9 TFEU, see also article 168 TFEU. Other mainstreaming provisions include for instance combating discrimination, equal treatment between men and women and environmental protection. All these policy aims must thus be integrated throughout all EU law and policy.

²² Greer and Jarman, fn. 20, p. 41.

Animal welfare protection goes back to the Treaty of Maastricht as well when a Declaration on animal welfare was added. This Declaration was replaced by a Protocol by the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997). The Treaty of Lisbon then added animal welfare protection to the list of horizontal ‘mainstreaming’ provisions as well. Animal welfare is, however, arguably the weakest of these provisions. Article 13 of the TFEU reads as follows:

In formulating and implementing the Union's agriculture, fisheries, transport, internal market, research and technological development and space policies, the Union and the Member States shall, since animals are sentient beings, pay full regard to the welfare requirements of animals, while respecting the legislative or administrative provisions and customs of the Member States relating in particular to religious rites, cultural traditions and regional heritage.

Thus, the requirement to consider animal welfare is restricted in two ways:

- 1) Member States may continue to protect certain national practices and;
- 2) the requirement to consider animal protection is restricted to specific areas.

In this light, the Court considered it not to be an enforceable general principle of EU law.²³ This means that animal welfare protection may for instance not be enforced upon the EU legislature even if it would adopt legislation with an insufficiently high level of protection. However, the Court did specify the legislation would not escape judicial control altogether. Since animal welfare has been recognised as legitimate public interest objective, it must be taken into account and balanced with other interests at stake.²⁴ As such, it could be part of the assessment of whether the legislature has respected the principle of proportionality. The case concerned the Union’s non-vaccination policy for cows for foot and mouth disease, and the Court indeed verified whether the legislature had taken full account of the requirements of animal welfare when considering various possible policy measures.²⁵

Although the case predates the adoption of Article 13 TFEU, the language used is mostly similar. Instead of “full account”, EU institutions and Member States should pay “full regard” to the welfare requirements of animals. However, as Vapnek and Purnhagen point out, the provision suffers from a lack of concretisation.²⁶ Concepts such as “full regard” but also “sentient beings” and “welfare requirements” are neither defined in the text of the provisions itself, nor in subsequent legislation. As such, it is unclear what the provision requires from policymakers and legislators alike. Even if legislation is subject to limited judicial control, it is unclear how animal welfare should be weighed against other public interests. Nevertheless, article 13 TFEU may be judicially enforceable, but the provision puts a significant responsibility on the EU legislature. It provides no independent legal basis to act however. Animal welfare is thus a public interest that must be realized in the context of other EU policies.

²³ Case C-189/01 *Jippes*, ECLI:EU:C:2001:420.

²⁴ Case C- 219/07 *Nationale Raad van Dierenkwekers en Liefhebbers VZW*, ECLI:EU:C:2008:353, par. 27.

²⁵ Case C-189/01 *Jippes*, ECLI:EU:C:2001:420, par. 85.

²⁶ J. Vapnek and K.P. Purnhagen, ‘Animal welfare in EU law: scope and purpose of Article 13 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union’, *European Law Review* 2024 (49) 2, p. 189.

4. Level 2: EU legislation

The Treaties have thus established public health, animal welfare and the internal market as the key public interests in the field, but it has been for the EU legislature to balance these interests. As Krämer observes, this is an ongoing battle. Especially the balance between the public health (and environmental) interest on the one hand and the internal market interest on the other is the subject of much dispute. The former is reflected in the prevention and precautionary principles.²⁷ The internal market interest is operationalized through risk assessment, possibly including cost-benefit analyses, in order to ensure trade in substances and products.²⁸

The subsequent sections will explore how the EU legislature has struck such balances in relation to specific products, substances or other specific legislation. First, the directive on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes will be assessed as it provides a general regulatory framework for animal testing in the EU. Next, the EU regulations on chemicals and their risks will be examined. Some of these regulations are of a more general nature (because of their wider scope), whereas others are limited to regulating only certain product categories. The general regulations will be discussed first. The Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) is general in nature as it offers a comprehensive framework to gather information and manage risks of chemical substances across sectors (4.2.1). The Regulation on the classification, labelling, and packaging of chemical substances and mixtures is equally broad as it covers all hazardous substances and mixtures, regardless of their specific use (4.2.2). The three product-specific acts are the Plant Protection Products Regulation (PPPR: 4.2.3); the Cosmetics Regulation (4.2.4) and the Biocides Regulation (4.2.5). This chapter ends with some general conclusions on these legislative acts.

EU legislation is ultimately interpreted by the European Court of Justice. When provisions lack clarity, the Court may be called upon to shape the legislative framework by elaborating provisions further and give specific meaning thereto. These interpretations are legally binding and thus form an integral part of the legislative framework.²⁹ The Court applies accepted interpretation techniques, such as the textual and historical interpretation methods (whereby the literal text and the legislature's decision-making respectively are considered). But the Court frequently relies on another technique: the teleological method of interpretation. When applying this method, the Court will interpret EU legislation in the light of its central objectives and may give less weight to other factors, such as the actual intentions of the legislature or even the literal meaning of legislative provisions. Instead, this approach appreciates the system of the law and thereby serves the consistency of EU legislation. This concerns, firstly, the internal consistency of legislative acts. The complexity of the EU's legislative procedure and the multiplicity of interests represented therein

²⁷ These principles are included in article 191 TFEU on environmental protection (which has as one of its aims the protection of human health). The precautionary principle entails that the EU institutions should act if it is suspected that a product or substance may be harmful for humans or the environment even in cases in which there is no definitive scientific evidence (yet).

²⁸ L. Krämer and C. Badger, *EU Environmental Law* (9th ed.), London: Bloomsbury Publishing (2024), p. 227.

²⁹ Article 19 TEU: "It shall ensure that in the interpretation and application of the Treaties the law is observed."

regularly results in legislation that is difficult to access and understand. The Court's teleological interpretation can then offer a useful way out.

A good example is the Court's decision in a case on a registration file under the REACH regulation (discussed below).³⁰ The competent authority had asked the registrant to supplement its registration dossier with a study involving animal testing. The Court held that, given the overarching objective of the REACH regulation to replace, reduce, or refine testing on vertebrate animals, the registrant was not only permitted but also required to respond to the competent authority's request using information obtained through means other than animal testing. Despite the precise wording of the authority's request and the absence of an explicit provision in the Regulation allowing such an approach, the Court determined that the legislative objective was the decisive factor.

4.1 Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes

This Directive was adopted in September 2010 and replaced an earlier directive dating back to 1986. That earlier directive was considered in need of revision, first and foremost in the light of growing disparities between the Member States. Some Member States had adopted measures to increase the level of animal welfare protection whereas others had remained at the minimum level prescribed for by the directive.³¹ This caused the internal market to function less well. The legislature advanced other arguments as well, such as scientific knowledge that had come available on the factors influencing animal welfare as well as the capacity of animals to sense and express pain, suffering, distress and lasting harm. Also the changing public perception in certain Member States to increase levels of animal protection was put forward as a reason to change the regulatory framework.³² The old directive did not have as its concrete aim to abolish animal testing. Rather, it sought to regulate the use of animals for experimental and other scientific purposes; to improve the controls on the use of laboratory animals, and to set minimum standards for housing and care, and for the training of personnel.

The new Directive does not introduce a direct ban on animal testing either, but – importantly – specifies that the final goal is that of **full replacement** (emphasis added) *of procedures on live animals for scientific and educational purposes as soon as it is scientifically possible to do so*.³³ At the same time, it acknowledges that it is currently not yet possible to achieve that goal and that the use of live animals continues to be necessary to protect human and animal health and the environment. This does not take away the fact that the new directive has further specified the general aim of the legislative act which is to protect animals used for scientific or educational purposes (art 1 (1)), ultimately resulting in a complete ban. This has important implications for the content of the directive and the wording of its provisions, but equally for judicial review. The Court's teleological approach, which has been explained above, implies that the concrete provisions of the directive will be assessed by the Court in light of this aim.

³⁰ Case C-471/18 P *Duitsland/Eso Raffinage*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:48.

³¹ Consideration 1 of the new directive.

³² Consideration 9 of the directive.

³³ Consideration 10 of the directive.

The Directive's higher ambition compared to its predecessor is reflected in a broader scope. The new Directive includes foetal organisms and cephalopods, which were not covered by the old directive.³⁴ The central principle of the Directive is the principle of replacement, reduction and refinement (the 3Rs) laid down in article 4. It reads as follows:

1. Member States shall ensure that, wherever possible, a scientifically satisfactory method or testing strategy, not entailing the use of live animals, shall be used instead of a procedure.
2. Member States shall ensure that the number of animals used in projects is reduced to a minimum without compromising the objectives of the project.
3. Member States shall ensure refinement of breeding, accommodation and care, and of methods used in procedures, eliminating or reducing to the minimum any possible pain, suffering, distress or lasting harm to the animals.
4. This Article shall, in the choice of methods, be implemented in accordance with Article 13.

Article 13 (1) provides that a Member State shall ensure that alternative methods, recognised under EU legislation, must be used. It has been argued that the interpretation of the term "wherever possible" in article 4 (1) would be generally similar to the old directive that prescribed that alternative methods should be used when these would be "reasonably and practicably available".³⁵ However, it could well be argued that the "wherever possible" in the new directive should be interpreted in a broader manner, to allow for alternatives to animal testing to be easier adopted and implemented. The argument for such a broader interpretation would be that the directives differ in their objectives. As mentioned above, the central objective of the old directive was merely to regulate animal testing, while the new directive explicitly introduces the ultimate aim to completely abolish animal testing. In light of the Court's teleological approach, this has implications for how this provision should be read and public authorities and private individuals should thus not conclude too easily that alternative methods are not possible to achieve the result sought.

The remaining of the Directive reflects a stricter approach to animal testing as well. The Directive limits the purposes for which animal testing may be used (article 5). Chapter II contain additional rules for the use of specific animal groups. The starting point is that these groups of animals are not used, unless an exception applies. These groups are:

- Endangered species (article 7);
- Non-human primates (article 8);
- Wild animals (art. 9);
- Animals bred for use in procedures; and
- Stray and feral animals (article 11).

Chapter III of the Directive sets standards for the treatment of animals, and Chapter IV (the most extensive chapter) regulates the substantive and procedural aspects of the

³⁴ T. Hartung, 'Comparative analysis of the revised Directive 2010/63/EU for the protection of laboratory animals with its predecessor 86/609/EEC - a t4 report', *Altex* 2010, pp. 285-303 (at p. 288).

³⁵ T. Hartung, 'Comparative analysis of the revised Directive 2010/63/EU for the protection of laboratory animals with its predecessor 86/609/EEC - a t4 report', *Altex* 2010, fn 34, p. 290.

authorization of procedures on live animals for scientific and educational purposes. Chapter V contains provisions to prevent duplication and to stimulate the development of alternative approaches (and promote international cooperation in this context).

Despite the level of animal protection being ratcheted up, the Directive still contains elements of Member States' discretion. Article 2 gives Member States the possibility to apply stricter animal welfare standards. This possibility is, however, fairly limited, especially in comparison to the old minimum harmonization clause which allowed Member States to apply stricter animal welfare standards generally. Now, the Member States may only do so as long as it will not affect the functioning of the internal market (which is easily the case), but – even more importantly – only with regard to standards that had been in force on 9 November 2010 (shortly after the adoption of the Directive) and have been notified to the Commission. This leaves no room for the Member States to adopt stricter standards afterwards, e.g. in response to changing views in their national societies. In the choice of methods, article 13 seems to allow the Member States some more discretion as it acknowledges the right of Member States to prohibit certain types of methods. At the more detailed, technical level other choices are possible. Olson et al have demonstrated that the infrastructure for review and authorization which is left to the Member States has resulted in very different choices among them.³⁶

The Member States are generally limited, though, in the way they can further elaborate the directive. Indeed, the directive itself regulates many of the technical details which are necessary to ensure its proper functioning.³⁷ In doing so, the EU legislature did not opt for leaving these details to the Commission, as the EU's main executive rule-making authority, either. The Directive includes elaborate annexes in which these details are worked out, e.g. on the standards of care and accommodation for animals (Annex III) and the classification of severity of procedures (Annex VIII). By way of delegated acts (article 290 TFEU), the Commission may, however, update most of these annexes in order to ensure that these provisions reflect the state of technical and scientific progress (article 50). The Commission equally possesses the competence to adopt implementing measures (article 291 TFEU) on the requirements with regard to education, training and competence of breeders', suppliers' and users' staff; to adopt detailed rules regarding the Union Reference Laboratory, its duties and tasks and the charges it may collect; to establish a common format for submitting required information by Member States to the Commission on the implementation of the directive, statistical information and other specific information; and for the application of safeguard clauses.

³⁶ A.S. Olsson et al., 'Protecting Animals and Enabling Research in the European Union: An Overview of Development and Implementation of Directive 2010/63/EU', *ILAR Journal* 2016 (57) 3, pp. 347-357.

³⁷ In this regard, the directive exhibits characteristics typically associated with a regulation.

4.2 Legislation regulating access to the Internal market

4.2.1 Regulation on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)

The REACH regulation (Regulation 1907/2006/EC) entered into force in 2007 with the tri-fold objectives of safeguarding human health and the environment from hazardous chemicals; enhancing the competitiveness of the EU chemical industry and fostering innovation. The regulation aimed to consolidate and streamline existing legislation into a comprehensive framework, ensuring all chemicals would be covered while placing responsibility for their safety on the industry. Better enforcement has been equally a concern. Generally in EU environmental law, non-compliance procedures against Member States had been highly frequent³⁸, and specifically, the regulation of the chemicals industry had been plagued by deficient enforcement.³⁹ As such, the adoption of the REACH regulation has been a highly contentious issue, which not only involved critical questions on how to balance environmental and economic goals within the EU. In any event, the question what should be the division of authority between EU and national levels of governance - which had dominated the decision-making on environmental issues in the 1980s and 1990s - was definitely moved into the background.

The REACH regulation turned the responsibility for collecting data on the properties of substances – which previously rest on public authorities – on the companies that produce or import these substances into the EU. They are equally responsible for assessing hazards and potential risks. This information forms the basis of the registration request. This request may involve proposals for animal testing to gather the required information. The European Chemicals Agency (hereafter: ECHA), which is tasked with the implementation of REACH, will assess the registration dossier to see whether the standard information requirements are met, including the substance identity and composition and toxicological information. If testing is required, testing proposals will be published by ECHA for input by stakeholders. The ECHA then makes a draft decision which it submits to the competent authority of the Member State. The Member State Committee of the ECHA adopts the final decision and communicates this to the registrants.⁴⁰ After the revision and modification of the testing proposals, a rejection is extremely rare.⁴¹

The procedure is subject to the following substantive norms and principles on animal testing. Adopted prior to the Animal Protection Directive, the regulation neither includes a ban on animal testing nor sets a future objective to implement one. Instead, the

³⁸ F. Jacobs, 'The Role of the European Court of Justice in the Protection of the Environment', *Journal of Environmental Law* 2006 (18) 2, p. 201.

³⁹ V. Heyvaert, 'No Data, No Market. The Future of EU Chemicals Control under the REACH Regulation', *Legislation Note, Environmental Law Review* 2007 (9) 3, pp. 201-206.

⁴⁰ Katy Taylor, 'Food for Thought... Experiences of the REACH Testing Proposals System to Reduce Animal Testing', *ALTEX* 2014 (31) 2, p. 108.

⁴¹ Katy Taylor, 'Food for Thought... Experiences of the REACH Testing Proposals System to Reduce Animal Testing', *ALTEX* 2014 (31) 2, p. 113.

Regulation adheres to the ‘Three R’s’ approach: replacement, reduction and refinement of animal testing. Animal testing on vertebrate animals is permitted only a last-resort option (article 25 (1)); duplication of animal testing must be avoided (also addressed in article 25); and alternative testing methods are prioritized.⁴² This framework was influenced by the European Commission’s 2001 White Paper on the future chemicals policy⁴³ which highlighted concerns about the anticipated rise in animal testing due to stricter safety requirements for chemicals. At the time, the issue sparked significant debate across Europe. The Commission drew on the 3-R approach that had already been formulated in the 1950s by Russel and Burch.⁴⁴

As part of the REACH Refit assessment of 2018, the Commission found that the regulation could be improved in relation to the animal testing provisions.⁴⁵ According to the Commission, the ECHA should minimize animal testing in line with REACH’s provisions.⁴⁶ The European Ombudsman has criticized ECHA’s approach to animal testing as well, emphasizing that avoiding animal testing is a core objective of REACH.⁴⁷ This creates a conflict between REACH’s goal of minimizing animal testing and the fact that its standard information requirements are still primarily fulfilled through studies involving animal testing. The Animal Free Safety Assessment Collaboration (hereafter: AFSA) has sought to identify possible explanations. It mentioned the high burden of proof on the registrants and existing or non-animal data and tests often not being accepted.⁴⁸ Other criticism regarded the inconsistency of REACH with Regulation 1223/2009 on cosmetic ingredients. The latter Regulation imposes a ban on in vivo (animal) testing for cosmetic products.⁴⁹ The former can impose in vivo testing on the exact same ingredients.⁵⁰ This conflict could potentially be addressed in the forthcoming revision of REACH. The AFSA requested the ECHA to permit the fulfilments of REACH requirements only through non-animal testing for cosmetic only ingredients, to comply with Union objectives.⁵¹ This is not the only inconsistency that can be observed within the EU regulatory framework for chemical safety.⁵² Several chemical regulations prohibit the use of chemical substances altogether, whereas REACH provides companies with an

⁴² Article 13(1) of Regulation 1907/2006/EC, Annex XI.

⁴³ European Commission, *White Paper Strategy for a future Chemicals Policy*, COM(2001) 88 final.

⁴⁴ W.M.S. Russell and R.L. Burch, *The Principles of Humane Experimental Technique*, London: Methuen (1959), p. 238.

⁴⁵ European Commission, *REACH Refit Evaluation* (12 April 2018).

⁴⁶ European Commission, *REACH Refit Evaluation* (12 April 2018), p. 5.

⁴⁷ European Ombudsman, *Decision of the European Ombudsman closing the inquiry into complaint 1568/2012/(FOR)AN against the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)*, <http://www.ombudsman.europa.eu/cases/decision.faces/en/58549/html.bookmark>.

⁴⁸ This paragraph summarizes the findings of the article: The last resort requirement under REACH: From principle to practice, *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*.

⁴⁹ Article 18 of the Regulation 1223/2009/EC.

⁵⁰ J. Knight et al., ‘Continuing Animal Tests on Cosmetic Ingredients for REACH in the EU’, *ALTEX* 2021 (38) 4, pp. 653-668.

⁵¹ D.S. Macmillan et al., ‘The last resort requirement under REACH: From principle to practice’, *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 2024 (147).

⁵² N. De Sadeleer, *EU Environmental law and the Internal Market*, Oxford: Oxford University Press (2013), p. 50.

opportunity to place hazardous chemicals on the market when the risks can be ‘adequately controlled.’⁵³

Endocrine-disrupting chemicals (hereafter: EDCs) have gradually become recognized as a concern in the context of chemical safety. The Commission initially sought to develop a horizontal approach – applicable for all products – by developing general criteria for identifying EDCs.⁵⁴ This proved difficult to realize in practice, however, which made the Commission turn to a sector-specific (product-based) approach, resulting in differing regulatory requirements, e.g. with regard to data requirements.⁵⁵ In 2018, the Commission argued that ‘while the regulatory approaches differ, all legislations have allowed to effectively take actions on endocrine disruptors to avoid risks for human health and the environment.’⁵⁶ This claim has been contested, however.⁵⁷

The REACH regulation determines that EDCs are considered substances of very high concern and their use must be authorized prior to entering the internal market.⁵⁸ The authorization process necessitates demonstrating either that the associated risks are effectively controlled or that their socio-economic benefits outweigh those risks.⁵⁹ As of 2022⁶⁰ only 105 substances were identified and regulated as EDCs under REACH, which suggests that REACH has not yet reached its full potential in the regulation of EDCs.⁶¹ In 2019, the Parliament adopted a resolution on a comprehensive European Union framework on endocrine disruptors. The Parliament emphasized the need for a horizontal definition and pointed to the failures in the implementation of REACH. The high rate of non-compliant registration dossiers, delays in evaluations caused by missing data, and the lack of regulatory action on substances identified as posing serious risks to human health or the environment were highlighted.⁶² These shortcomings, which also result in insufficient efforts to minimise exposure to known or suspected endocrine disruptors, prompted a call for the European Chemicals Agency, the Commission, and Member States to take all necessary measures. In December 2023, the Commission proposed a ‘one substance, one assessment’ chemicals assessment reform, with a proposal for two new

⁵³ Article 57(2) of the REACH Regulation.

⁵⁴ C. Michel, ‘How to regulate endocrine disrupting chemicals? Feedback and future development’, *Elsevier Review* 2019 (7), p. 21.

⁵⁵ C. Michel, ‘How to regulate endocrine disrupting chemicals? Feedback and future development’, *Elsevier Review* 2019 (7), page 24.

⁵⁶ European Commission, *Endocrine Disruptors: Questions and Answers* (7 November 2018).

⁵⁷ C. Michel, ‘How to regulate endocrine disrupting chemicals? Feedback and future development’, *Elsevier Review* 2019 (7), p. 24.

⁵⁸ Article 57(f) of the REACH regulation.

⁵⁹ C. Duh-Leong et al., ‘The regulation of endocrine-disrupting chemicals to minimize their impact on health’, *Nature Reviews Endocrinology* 2023 (19) 10.

⁶⁰ European Environmental Bureau, & CHEM Trust. (2023). *Waiting for REACH: The negative impacts of delaying reform of EU chemical laws*. European Environmental Bureau. https://eeb.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/EEB-CT-Waiting-for-REACH_final-report.pdf

⁶¹ C. Duh-Leong et al., ‘The regulation of endocrine-disrupting chemicals to minimize their impact on health’, *Nature Reviews Endocrinology* 2023 (19) 10, p. 604.

⁶² European Parliament, *Resolution on a comprehensive European Union framework on endocrine disruptors* (18 April 2019), 2019/2683(RSP).

Regulations and one Directive.⁶³ A key element of this reform is the envisioned Common Data Platform held by the EU agencies, including the ECHA.

These reforms are part of a broader strategy based on the European Green Deal. In 2020, this resulted in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, which included an initiative for a major revision of the REACH regulation.⁶⁴ This revision is still ongoing and expected to continue well into 2025.⁶⁵ A legislative proposal has thus far not even been tabled.⁶⁶ The Commission's work programme for 2023 announced that the proposal would be pushed back to the fourth quarter of 2023.⁶⁷ This did not succeed and the Commission's work programme for 2024 did not even mention the REACH revision.⁶⁸ Recently, the environmental ministers in the Council reviewed the implementation of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and called for outstanding actions, including the delayed revision of REACH, to be adopted.⁶⁹ An NGO filed a complaint with the European Ombudsman asking the Commission to grant access to the impact assessment and opinions of the Regulatory Scrutiny Board concerning the REACH revision. The Commission had denied access to these documents on the basis of the protection of the decision making process and commercial interests. The Ombudsman rejected these exception grounds, however, referring to the fact that the EU courts have dismissed similar arguments. The Ombudsman equally emphasized the essential nature of public access to legislative documents for the functioning of democracy of the EU legal system.⁷⁰ The Commission

⁶³ European Commission – Press release, *Commission proposes 'one substance, one assessment' chemicals assessment reform for faster, simplified and transparent processes* (7 December 2023); Proposal for a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals COM(2023) 779 final; Proposal for a Regulation on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks and improving cooperation among Union agencies in the area of chemicals, COM(2023) 783 fin.; Proposal for a Directive on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks to the European Chemicals Agency, COM(2023) 781 fin.

⁶⁴ European Parliament, *Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In: A European Green Deal* (Q3 2020), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-chemicals-strategy>.

⁶⁵ European Parliament, *Revision of the Regulation on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). In: A European Green Deal* (Q4 2023 – 10.2024), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/reach-revision/report?sid=8501>.

⁶⁶ European Parliament, *Revision of the Regulation on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). In: A European Green Deal* (Q4 2023 – 9.2025), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/reach-revision/report?sid=9501>.

⁶⁷ European Commission, *Annexes to the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Commission work programme 2023*, COM(2022) 548 final.

⁶⁸ European Commission, *Annexes to the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Commission work programme 2024*, COM(2024) 638 final.

⁶⁹ European Parliament, *Revision of the Regulation on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). In: A European Green Deal* (Q4 2023 – 9.2025), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/reach-revision/report?sid=9501>. Council meeting of 14 October 2024.

⁷⁰ European Ombudsman, *Decision on how the European Commission dealt with two requests for public access to impact assessments and opinions of the Regulatory Scrutiny Board regarding the envisaged revision of the EU regulations on chemicals (REACH) and mercury (case 1053/2023/MIK)*, <https://www.ombudsman.europa.eu/en/decision/en/183548>.

has, meanwhile, been accused of maladministration and of being overly susceptible to corporate lobbying.⁷¹

The EP elections have obviously been a relevant factor for the delay as well. Moreover, the Commission that announced an ambitious reform of the Regulation is not the same as the current Commission that took office in 2024.⁷² Commission president Von der Leyen did announce her political guidelines for the new Commission which include a new chemicals industry package, aiming to ‘simplify REACH’ and to provide more legal clarity on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS).⁷³

The Inception impact assessment document is currently the only available official document regarding the revision.⁷⁴ It identifies problems with the authorisation procedure being too heavy and inflexible, posing a high burden on both companies and authorities. A significant negative impact on the control of risks is caused by communication deficits in the supply chains. The evaluation of registration dossiers and substances is deemed too complex and insufficient. Additionally, the restriction process is too slow to provide a satisfactory level of protection to consumers against the risks from hazardous substances. Finally, the enforcement in the Member States is mentioned as not being sufficiently effective. Non- animal testing is mentioned only once, as an alleviating factor to the increase in the administrative burden and compliance costs.

4.2.2 Regulation on the classification, labelling and packaging of dangerous substances (CLP)

As mentioned above, the Directive 67/548/EEC on the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances has been the first of the major legislations in the field of chemical safety. It reflected a balance in the internal market and public health objectives. It aimed at ‘protecting the public, and in particular workers using substances and preparations’, but was in the end limited to substances. The legislature acknowledged that for the internal market to function properly it would be necessary regulate all aspects of substances. This would however – according to the 1967 EU legislature – require so ‘many detailed measures’ that it would be better to start only with provisions on classification, packaging and labelling. In doing so, the legislature adopted a ‘patchwork’ strategy, a method now common for the EU legislature. This approach prioritizes feasibility over the creation of a comprehensive regulatory framework. A hallmark of this patchwork approach is the gradual, ‘organic’ evolution of these fragmented laws into more comprehensive and stringent legislation.

⁷¹ Vicky Cann Corporate Europe Observatory, *REACH Regulation- EU Commission’s failure to share full documents constitutes double-maladministration* (2024). See also: European Environmental Bureau Press Release, *Commission’s 2023 Work Programme caves under chemical and farm industry pressures* (18 October 2022), <https://eeb.org/commissions-2023-work-programme-caves-under-chemical-and-farm-industry-pressures/>.

⁷² ChemSec, *This is what delaying the REACH revision actually means*, <https://chemsec.org/this-is-what-delaying-the-reach-revision-actually-means/>.

⁷³ Ursula von der Leyen, *Europe’s Choice, Political Guidelines for the Next European Commission 2024-2029*, https://commission.europa.eu/about/commission-2024-2029/president-elect-ursula-von-der-leyen_en.

⁷⁴ Inception impact assessment, Ares(2021)2962933.

This approach marks the successor CLP as well. The CLP from 2008 (Regulation 1272/2008/EU) demonstrated a broader ambition though. It expanded the central objectives: environmental protection was added as a central objective and the public health rationale was broadened. It no longer specified workers, but simply referred to public health protection generally. The updated directive was, moreover, broader in scope. It covered not only dangerous substances but also mixtures. Lastly, the directive stressed the global context of the subject matter, referring to global harmonization at the level of the United Nations. The connection to this international level beyond the EU is twofold: the EU should align its regulatory frameworks to that of the UN and at the same time contribute to the latter and strive for other third countries to participate thereto. In the light of this higher ambition, the EU legislature decided to replace the 1967 directive by a regulation. Even though the legislature did not provide specific reasons, the shift is a significant one. It made the legislation no longer dependent on national transposition legislation and created a more uniform regulatory framework.

The Regulation foresaw a number of steps to assess the risks for hazardous substances and mixtures. The first, and for the purposes of this research the most important – step regarded the identification of hazards. The responsibility lied with the market actors themselves (manufacturers, importers and downstream users of a substance or mixture) who must determine the potential physical, health or environmental hazards (articles 5 and 6 of the Regulation). To this end, they must gather information. This information might come from existing studies (such as academic literature, studies carried out under REACH etc.); databases and industry information.⁷⁵ If these were, however, not available new studies might have to be conducted. The following steps which the Regulation foresaw were, consecutively, the classification, labeling and packaging requirements. The Regulation contained additional requirements as well, such as the obligation for manufactures and importers to notify ECHA for inclusion in the Classification and Labelling Inventory.

Returning to the first step – the identification of hazards – the Regulation contained various elements to avoid animal testing. Manufacturers, importers, and downstream users should, first, try to rely on existing information and thereby avoid duplicate testing.⁷⁶ Second, alternative testing was already prioritized over animal testing. According to the Guidance, this included methods such as in vitro tests, computational models (QSAR), and read-across approaches, where possible.⁷⁷ Article 7 provided in this regard that animal testing was only allowed when such alternative methods were not possible or provided no adequate levels of reliability and quality of data. Moreover, tests on non-human primates were prohibited for the purposes of the Regulation. Annex I – Classification and Labelling Requirements reflected this strategy to avoid animal testing as well.⁷⁸ All in all, with the principle to avoid duplicate testing and by giving priority to alternative testing the CLP Regulation aligned already well with the Animal testing directive. The “whenever possible”

⁷⁵ See: European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), *Guidance on the Application of the CLP Criteria*, November 2024.

⁷⁶ Consideration 20 and further of the regulation; articles 7, 8 and 25 of the regulation.

⁷⁷ Fn. 75.

⁷⁸ See e.g. provisions 1.1.1.4, 3.3.2.4 and 3.3.3.1.2 of Annex I.

clause – to be found across the regulatory framework - qualified the phasing out of animal testing, however.

Revision of the CLP⁷⁹

The CLP Regulation has recently been revised. The final text containing the amendments was signed on the 23 October 2024 (Regulation 2024/2865/EU). This revision was motivated by factors such as the European Green Deal, evolving scientific understanding, public health and environmental concerns, and the need for regulatory updates. The Green Deal emphasizes the importance of providing a higher level of protection for human health and the environment against hazardous chemicals. The substantive changes are the following.

1. **Emerging Hazards and New Hazard Classes:** One of the main updates to the CLP is the inclusion of new hazard classes. These categories cover substances such as endocrine disruptors and chemicals that are persistent, bio-accumulative, and toxic (PBT) or very persistent, very bio-accumulative (vPvB). These substances pose long-term risks that current regulations may not fully address, particularly in terms of human health and environmental impacts.
2. **Enhanced protection levels.** One example is the improvement of classification and labelling requirements, which will now aim to better consider the *cumulative* effects of exposure to multiple chemicals. This change is crucial for assessing risks more comprehensively and improving public and environmental safety.
3. **Animal Welfare and Testing Alternatives:** Another significant aspect of the reform is its focus on reducing reliance on animal testing. The amended Article 7 emphasizes prioritizing non-animal testing methods alongside traditional animal and human testing. Additionally, Article 53 introduces a commitment on part of the Commission to regularly evaluate the development of alternative approaches (preferably within 18 months from the moment of adoption at the level of the UN). To this end, the Commission has been mandated to adopt delegated acts to update the latest non-animal data criteria in the CLP. However, while the language has been strengthened, concerns persist regarding the potential for increased animal testing. For instance, new hazard classifications like those for endocrine disruptors might lead to greater testing demands if alternative methods are not fully implemented. Despite the push for new approaches, the updated provisions do not yet establish a clear path toward an outright ban on animal testing.

In summary, the CLP revision has sought to address emerging chemical hazards, enhance protection in line with the Green Deal, and promote animal welfare through non-animal testing alternatives. However, challenges remain in ensuring these ambitions lead to reduced animal testing in practice.⁸⁰

⁷⁹ European Commission, *Proposal of 19 December 2021*, COM(2022) 748 final. The EP reached a provisional deal on the regulation in December 2023, but have not been able to finalize the legislative process before the EP election in 2024.

⁸⁰ Health and Environment Alliance (HEAL), *Analysis of the draft European Parliament ENVI report regarding the legal proposal for reform of the CLP legislation*, <https://www.env-health.org/wp->

4.2.3 Plant Protection Products Regulation

Regulation 1107/2009/EU governs the authorization, sale, and use of plant protection products (PPPs) within the European Union. These include chemicals like pesticides, herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides which are used to protect crops from pests, diseases, and weeds.

The main objectives of the Regulation are⁸¹:

- to ensure a high level of protection for human health, animal health, and the environment.
- to guarantee the safe and effective use of PPPs in agriculture and horticulture.
- to promote sustainable agriculture by encouraging the development and use of less hazardous products and more environmentally friendly alternatives.

To achieve this, the regulation creates a framework which is mainly procedural in nature (as opposed to a legislative framework that would itself decide on which chemicals would be allowed). Only chemicals (active substances in the terminology of the regulation) that meet certain safety standards are allowed in the EU internal market. To this end, the Regulation establishes an authorization procedure. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) evaluate substances for potential risks to human health, animals, and the environment. A positive decision means that Member States may authorize specific PPPs that contain the substance concerned. Thus, the main rationale of the authorization procedure is public health protection. Animal welfare is closely associated as its primary goal in this context is to protect animals that may be exposed to substances that are part of plant protection products. Animal testing is a different matter and is regulated separately. The Regulation contains no ban, but Article 61 of the Regulation contains provisions on preventing duplicate testing and article 62 enhances the stringency of these provisions for animal testing that involves vertebrate animals. Apart from the requirement that animal testing involving vertebrate animals may only be undertaken if no other methods are available, the other requirements all regard avoiding test duplication. The PPP Regulation thus prioritizes the public health and related environmental and animal welfare concerns over the protection of animals used for animal testing. The legislature has evidently considered the tracing of harmful effects of substances in plant protection products as a key priority. The actual balance between the internal market objective (free movement of substances and plant protection products) and public health protection depends, however, on the actual decision-making on concrete substances.

There are plans to revise the PPPR as well, but the revision process is not as far advanced as the CLP revision. The Commission has not yet tabled a proposal. Nevertheless, there is

content/uploads/2023/05/Briefing_CLP-reform-1.pdf; Eurogroup for animals, *European Parliament debates and votes on CLP revision*, <https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/news/european-parliament-debates-and-votes-clp-revision>.

⁸¹ See the recitals of the Regulation and article 1.

a quite recent evaluation of the Regulation.⁸² Comparable to the CLP, the EU Green Deal is a main driver of the revision. Also the so-called Farm-to-Fork Strategy, which aims at making food systems more sustainable and the need to reduce the environmental and health impacts of pesticides, provide motives for the reform. Some contentious (re-)authorization processes, most notably on glyphosate in 2017,⁸³ have equally fuelled the need to revise the regulation. In this light, it is no surprise that the revision focuses on reducing chemical pesticides, e.g. in the light of growing concerns over biodiversity (in particular pollinators such as bees). Risk assessment will thus be more comprehensive and strict, i.a. by including cumulative exposure to multiple chemicals, including potential endocrine disruptors and substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative. By thus expanding the scope of the public health interest, the revision is similar to that of the CLP revision. It equally seeks to accommodate the internal market interest by easing the authorization process for low-risk plant protection products, including biologicals (natural substances or organisms used in pest control), which could be used as alternatives to conventional chemicals. At the time of writing this report it remains unclear, however, what a revision would bring for the provisions on animal testing.

4.2.4 The Cosmetics Products Regulation (CPR)

The Cosmetics Regulation seeks to ensure that cosmetics marketed in the EU are safe from a public health perspective. To this end, it includes:

- lists of prohibited substances (Annex II) and restricted substances (Annex III);
- the requirement that each cosmetic product has a designated Responsible Person (RP) who ensures compliance with the regulation;
- the obligation to carry out a safety assessment (article 10) on the basis of which it can be concluded that the cosmetic product is safe for human health ‘when used under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use’. Access to the market is subject to a notification process (article 13 of the Regulation), rather than to the more complex authorization processes we find under the other regulations.

The Regulation ‘comprehensively’ harmonizes legislation in order to ‘achieve an internal market for cosmetic products while ensuring a high level of human health protection’ (consideration 4). This consideration thus signals the lack of national discretion in the implementation of the Regulation and is thereby stricter compared to the previous regulations.

The Regulation is also the strictest on animal testing. Article 18 fully bans animal testing for cosmetic products and ingredients. The ban applies to testing within the EU and to any products imported into the EU. The regulation also includes a marketing ban, which

⁸² No proposal yet, but from the 2020 evaluation some issues for revision may be identified:

European Commission, *Evaluation of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 on the placing of plant protection products on the market and of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides*, 20.5.2020, COM(2020)208.

⁸³ T. van den Brink, ‘Danger! Glyphosate may Expose Weaknesses in Institutional Systems: EU Legislation and Comitology in the Face of a Controversial Reauthorisation’, *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2020 (11(3)), pp. 436-449.

prohibits the sale of cosmetics in the EU if they, or their ingredients, have been tested on animals. This applies even if the testing occurred outside of the EU. The animal testing ban has been introduced in phases: animal testing on finished cosmetic products was banned in 2004, followed by a ban on animal testing on cosmetic ingredients in 2009. In 2013 a complete marketing ban came into force. The Regulation equally requires the Commission to monitor the development, validation and legal acceptance of alternative methods (article 35 of the Regulation). The strict animal ban, including for ingredients, can be problematic in light of other legislation. Indeed, for cosmetics ingredients that are also used in other products or applications, animal testing may still be required under other legislation, such as the Plant Protection Products Regulation, the Biocidal Products Regulation or REACH.

The Cosmetics Regulation will be revised as well, as was announced in the Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.⁸⁴ To this end, the Commission launched a public consultation in 2021. The revision would i.a. aim at combination effects (i.e. interactions between different chemicals present in cosmetics); improve safety assessments; review the definition of nanomaterials used in the CPR to ensure coherent terminology across chemicals legislation and improve the labelling of cosmetic products.⁸⁵ Also the alignment with the Treaty of Lisbon, in terms of granting implementing and delegated powers to the Commission would be part of the revision.

Up until now, however, the Commission has not yet tabled a proposal.

4.2.5 The Biocidal Products Regulation

The Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR - Regulation 528/2012/EU) aims to improve the functioning of the internal market through the harmonisation of the rules on the making available on the market and the use of biocidal products and to ensure a high level of protection of both human and animal health and the environment (article 1 of the Regulation). Biocidal products covered are disinfectants, preservatives, pest control products, and other biocidal products. Its scope is thereby close to that of the PPPR. Whereas the latter applies to products used in agriculture to protect crops, the BPR applies to various settings, including homes, industries, and healthcare. The BPR equally includes a two-step authorization process, whereby approval of active substances is done at the EU level (articles 12-16), and product authorization at either the national level or at the EU level. Authorization in one Member States may, through the application of the mutual recognition principle give access to other Member States as well.

Some categories of substances are prohibited (article 5):

- Substances which have been classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction under the CLP regulation
- Substances identified as having endocrine-disrupting properties

⁸⁴ European Commission, *Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Towards a Toxic-Free Environment*, 14.10.2020, COM(2020) 667 final.

⁸⁵ European Parliament, *Revision of the Cosmetic Products Regulation (Q4 2022 – 9.2025)*, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-the-cosmetic-products-regulation>.

- Substances that are persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic (PBT), or very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) according to the REACH Regulation
- Other substances that raise concerns equivalent to the above categories, particularly those that may have serious and irreversible effects on humans or non-target organisms.

Article 5 of the Regulation further requires the Commission to adopt delegated acts to specify the scientific criteria for determining endocrine-disrupting properties. In 2015, the General Court of the European Union held that the Commission had failed to fulfil its obligations to do so.⁸⁶ The General Court observed that the ‘Commission had a clear, precise and unconditional obligation to adopt delegated acts for the specification of the scientific criteria for the determination of the endocrine-disrupting properties’. These were subsequently adopted.⁸⁷

The Regulation leaves room for animal testing. The provisions are yet again different from the other regulations though. Article 62 contains the following principles:

- Animal testing (on vertebrates) may only be undertaken as a last resort.
- Animal tests are subject to prior approval by the competent authorities and their need must be properly justified.
- Testing duplication must be avoided by mandatory data sharing.
- Possibility of waiving of data requirements (article 20) if it is not scientifically necessary to supply the data or the data are not necessary owing to the exposure associated with the proposed uses.

In an overview report from 2019, the Commission noted several problems in the Member States with regard to the functioning of the Regulation including: the complexity of the review processes, poor quality of dossiers, lack of synchronised procedures and insufficient staff resources.⁸⁸ In a report published in 2021,⁸⁹ the Commission mentioned as problems, the slow progress with the evaluation of active substances included in the review programme and the continuous substantial delays in both active substance approval and product authorisation processes as well as the very limited level of innovation on new active substances. Despite these problems (or perhaps as these problems do not result from the content of the Regulation), there is no revision of the Regulation foreseen.

4.2.6 Conclusions EU legislation

Most EU legislation, apart from the CLP regulation, is already a bit older. This means that that endocrine disruption as a possible hazard class as such has not been included in these legislative acts as such.

⁸⁶ Case T-521/14 *Sweden v. Commission*, ECLI:EU:T:2015:976.

⁸⁷ See below for the eventual delegated acts.

⁸⁸ DG Health and Food Safety, *Overview Report Biocides*, https://www.eerstekamer.nl/overig/20200612/overview_report_biocides/document.

⁸⁹ European Commission, *Report on the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 of the European Parliament and the Council concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products*, COM (2021) 287 final.

The criteria for identifying endocrine disruptors were adopted in 2018 under the Plant Protection Products Regulation and Biocidal Products Regulation, which build on the IPCS/WHO definition. Criteria set under PPPR and BPR may provide a starting point for a future cross-sectorial definition in EU legislation.

Rather than providing a single, integrated regulatory system, the EU legislative framework is highly diversified, comprising multiple sectoral legislative acts alongside a separate directive on animal testing. These sectoral acts often overlap. For example, the REACH Regulation and the CLP Regulation may intersect with the product-specific regulations. Similarly, since product regulations govern both end products and their ingredients (substances), overlaps can arise when the same ingredients are used in different end products.

The legislative acts also adopt varied approaches to animal testing. The Cosmetics Regulation, for instance, imposes a strict ban on animal testing, while other legislative acts permit such testing under specific conditions. These other acts further vary in their scope and requirements for animal testing, leading to inconsistencies that may cause practical challenges, as the Fitness check demonstrates.⁹⁰

Nonetheless, the sectoral approach offers flexibility in balancing public health, animal welfare, and market considerations. Such variations in priorities can be justified by differences in economic significance, societal interests, and other factors relevant to the products in question.

5. Level 3. Executive rule-making

The Commission has adopted a range of rule-making acts under the legislation discussed in the previous section. These have mostly taken the form of implementing acts, but a couple of delegated acts have seen the light as well. These acts further flesh out the normative content of the legislative act on which they are based (implementing acts) or supplement the regulatory framework it has created (delegated acts).⁹¹ In the following, I will discuss only those which are relevant for the purposes of this research, i.e. address endocrine disruption and/or animal testing.

A key delegated act in this regard concerns Delegated regulation 2017/2100/EU on scientific criteria for the determination of endocrine disrupting properties.⁹² It seeks to prohibit active substances, safeners and synergists that have endocrine disrupting properties which may cause adverse effects in humans. It has been based on the Biocides Regulation that included the specific obligation for the Commission to adopt such criteria before 2014.⁹³

⁹⁰ European Commission, *FITNESS CHECK on endocrine disruptors Accompanying the document Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability*, SWD(2020) 251 final.

⁹¹ See section 2.

⁹² Delegated Regulation 2017/2100/EU.

⁹³ Article 5(3) of Regulation 528/2012/EU.

The Regulation aligns with WHO definitions, both for “endocrine disruptors” and for “adverse effects”. The conclusion that certain substances etc. do not have endocrine disrupting properties and/or that these do not cause adverse effects in humans must be based on human and/or animal evidence, ‘therefore allowing for the identification of both known and presumed endocrine disrupting substances’.⁹⁴ We thus witness a rebalancing of the public health against the animal welfare public interest, resulting in animal testing to (re)gain importance. An implementing act with an identical content was adopted a year later under the PPPR.⁹⁵

As we saw in the preceding chapter, the REACH regulation contains no specific provisions on endocrine disruption, but the classification of an active substance as a substance of very high concern can be attributable to endocrine disrupting qualities. In 2017 the Commission adopted Implementing Regulation 2017/735/EU on testing methods for the procedures regulated by the REACH regulation. This Regulation, amending an earlier one to bring EU legislation in line with technical progress as reflected by the evolving OECD standards, is relevant for both the animal testing and the endocrine disruption perspective. It introduces (or amends) 20 testing methods and discontinues 6 others. In line with the Animal welfare directive, which had been adopted some years earlier, the Regulation reflects the 3Rs principle, e.g. by prescribing a ‘weight-of-the-evidence’ analysis, which must demonstrate the need for in-vivo testing first (or otherwise abstain from it). It equally includes requirements for situations in which in-vivo testing is necessary.⁹⁶ Under point C.48, the Regulation includes the implementation of the OECD Fish Short Term Reproduction Assay, capable of detecting endocrine modalities. It is elaborated to enable an effective tracing and assessing of endocrine disruption qualities on the one hand, but includes on the other a multitude of aspects and requirements that seek to minimize the negative effects on the fish involved in the testing. In 2021, an Implementing regulation has been adopted under the REACH regulation to revise the entries for certain phthalates, which are known for their endocrine-disrupting qualities.⁹⁷ The regulation subjects the use of these substances to a stricter regulatory framework by removing earlier exemptions for specific uses.

Only in 2023, the Commission adopted a delegated regulation under the CLP Regulation to introduce new hazard classes and criteria for the classification, labeling, and packaging of chemical substances and mixtures.⁹⁸ It introduces known or presumed endocrine disruptors and suspected endocrine disruptors as new hazard classes and further builds on the regulations adopted under the BPR and the PPPR.

Lastly, executive rule-making acts increasingly include prohibitions for specific substances identified as endocrine disruptors. The EU maintains a list of substances identified as

⁹⁴ Consideration 4 of Regulation 2017/2100/EU.

⁹⁵ Implementing Regulation 2018/605/EU.

⁹⁶ A similar regulation, Delegated regulation 2021/525/EU, has subsequently been adopted under the BPR.

⁹⁷ Implementing Regulation 2021/2045/EU. Both regulations have been based on a joint impact assessment of 15 June 2016, SWD (2016) 212.

⁹⁸ Regulation 2023/707/EU.

endocrine disruptors by such delegated and implementing acts.⁹⁹ Such prohibitions are not just relevant from a public health perspective, but equally from an animal welfare perspective as they equally end the

All in all, executive rule-making is essentially important for the further shaping and elaboration of the balance between the internal market, the public health and the animal welfare interests.

6. Level 4. Soft law/ agencies

The Commission is a key source for the ‘production’ of soft law. In the form of Commission communications it may e.g. issue green and white papers such as the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability to prepare or to present policy proposals. These may involve the assessment and evaluation of existing legislation with a view to possible amendments thereto. The Fitness check on endocrine disruptors accompanying the Chemicals Strategy sought, inter alia, to assess whether EU legislation is coherent in its approach to endocrine disruptors and whether it adequately protects the environment and public health sufficiently by minimizing exposure to EDs.¹⁰⁰ It concluded that, while there was room improvement in terms of simplification, consolidation, burden reduction and better communication of the principles guiding risk management of EDs, no significant issues in the identification of EDs across sectors had been identified.

The role of the agencies, ECHA and EFSA, is a relevant factor as well in this context. As indicated in the introductory section, agencies impact the content of regulatory standards in basically two distinct ways. First, the agencies have crucial role in preparing formal decision-making by the Commission.

A clear example is the identification of substances of very high concern (SVHCs) under the REACH Regulation. As previously explained, ECHA prepares an Annex XV dossier for this purpose and conducts a risk assessment to support the proposal for inclusion in the Candidate List. However, it is the European Commission that adopts the final decision to include a substance in Annex XIV. Only this decision has binding legal effect. Nevertheless, ECHA’s role in the process is highly influential, as its scientific assessments and recommendations significantly shape the outcome.

A second key function of the agencies lies in the issuance of soft law instruments, which serve to supplement and clarify binding legislative acts. These instruments guide industry stakeholders, consumers, and national authorities in the consistent and effective application of EU legislation. This is a well-established and widespread practice, with **guidance documents** being the most common format for such soft law tools, e.g. with regard to the

⁹⁹ *List I: Substances identified as endocrine disruptors at EU level*, available from: <https://edlists.org/the-ed-lists/list-i-substances-identified-as-endocrine-disruptors-by-the-eu>.

¹⁰⁰ European Commission, *FITNESS CHECK on endocrine disruptors Accompanying the document Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability*, SWD(2020) 251 final.

REACH registration process.¹⁰¹ These guidances are oftentimes subject to elaborate decision-making processes, involving extensive stakeholder consultation for instance. For the purposes of this report, two guidances warrant further elaboration. The first is the guidance document adopted by ECHA and EFSA jointly for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC)No 1107/2009.¹⁰² The document describes how to gather, evaluate and consider all relevant information for the assessment; how to conduct a mode of action (MoA) analysis; and how to apply a weight of evidence (WoE) approach, in order to establish whether the ED criteria are fulfilled. To this end, the document contains detailed information, including on testing. Section 4 discusses different testing methods and includes a discussion of how various in vivo assays may produce evidence relevant for the assessment of ED properties. This section is based on OECD guidance and follows the classification into five levels of testing methods whereby level 5 represents the most intrusive form.¹⁰³ The European Commission has recognized the guidance as a ‘major milestone’ and as a starting point for subsequent cross-sectoral definitions of EDs.¹⁰⁴ The European Parliament, however, discussed criticisms that had been raised by stakeholders. This included the high level of proof needed for qualifying a substance as having ED properties; the limited scope of what are considered to be ED and the applicable criteria.¹⁰⁵

The second relevant guidance is ECHA’s Guidance on the Use of Alternatives to Animal Testing.¹⁰⁶ It seeks to avoid unnecessary testing, ensure sufficient information is available for classification and risk assessment and assists companies in applying alternative testing strategies. With regard to the last element, the guide contains detailed instructions on documenting each alternative method to meet regulatory requirements. As such, it is fully in line with REACH’s aim to minimize animal testing. Still, there has been criticism on ECHA. ‘*There is an increased perception that ECHA does not sufficiently consider the scientific developments in the field and does not devote sufficient attention and resources to the promotion of alternative methods to animal testing*’, according to a report from 2022.¹⁰⁷ For endocrine disruption specifically, challenges to the acceptance of non-animal approaches have been identified.¹⁰⁸ These challenges stem from the inherent difficulty in demonstrating the absence of endocrine-disrupting properties of substances, which consequently increases reliance on animal testing.

¹⁰¹ European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), *Registration*, <https://echa.europa.eu/en/regulations/reach/registration>.

¹⁰² EFSA Journal Volume 16, Issue 6 (Jun 2018).

¹⁰³ Namely: in vivo assays providing more comprehensive data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints over more extensive parts of the life cycle of the organism.

¹⁰⁴ European Commission, *FITNESS CHECK on endocrine disruptors Accompanying the document Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability*, SWD(2020) 251 final, section, 4.2.1.

¹⁰⁵ European Parliament Research Service (EPRS), *Endocrine disruptors. An overview of the latest developments at European level in the context of plant protection products*, April 2019, p. 25.

¹⁰⁶ European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), *ECHA and the promotion of alternative methods to animal testing*, 29 September 2022.

¹⁰⁷ European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), *ECHA and the promotion of alternative methods to animal testing*, 29 September 2022, p. 2.

¹⁰⁸ K. Stoykova, ‘Towards Non-Animal Testing in European Regulatory Toxicology: An Introduction to the REACH Framework and Challenges in Implementing the 3Rs’, *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2025, pp. 1-31, at p. 12.

The role of agencies and soft law is an important element for and of the applicable regulatory framework. Compliance with all the higher levels of the regulatory framework is required and the examples of the ECHA and EFSA guidance suggest that no major issues have emerged in this regard. The criticism on the agencies for their slow and limited acceptance of non-animal testing methods must thus be explained from other factors. One explanation may be that the legislative framework as a whole is not fully oriented towards a complete ban on animal testing. It rather accepts the use of animal testing to the extent it is necessary for public health reasons. This trade-off impacts the work of the agencies too.

Another explanation may lie in the interface between the legislative framework and its concrete *application* by the agencies. In that case, the agencies would be reluctant in accepting non-animal testing methods, which would often mean that organizations would in practice still have to resort to animal testing. This is suggested by Stoykova who claims that, in the context of REACH authorization procedures, ECHA generally still requires animal testing and only accepts NAMs if these are used in international guidelines.¹⁰⁹ The legislative framework grants agencies discretion to make individual decisions regarding specific testing methods. While such a reluctant administrative practice would clearly complicate the ultimate goal of phasing out animal testing, it is important to note that it would as such thus not necessarily be incompatible with the legislative framework.

7. General conclusions

Numerous studies have highlighted significant barriers in the transition toward animal-free toxicological testing. Stoykova elaborates four main challenges:

- a) Inadequate and sometimes contradictory legislation
- b) Lengthy and burdensome validation processes for new approach methodologies (NAMs)
- c) Limited acceptance of NAMs by ECHA
- d) Planned legislation that may actually lead to increased animal testing.

While the second and third issues fall outside the scope of this report, it is important to underscore that ECHA and other competent authorities are legally obliged to apply the legislative framework in its entirety. As the case discussed above illustrates, the European Court of Justice has demonstrated its willingness to enforce this obligation. Although technical and practical challenges—which at the very least delay the transition to non-animal testing—are likely to persist, it is important to note that the legislative framework, along with the Court's enforcement role, imposes incentives for this transition.

¹⁰⁹ K. Stoykova, 'Towards Non-Animal Testing in European Regulatory Toxicology: An Introduction to the REACH Framework and Challenges in Implementing the 3Rs', *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2025, p. 13. See also fn 188 of her article in which this argument is supported with quantitative data.

In terms of substance, the objectives and principles of the legislative framework are relatively clear. Across relevant legislation, the 3R principles (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) are embedded, and animal testing is permitted only as a last resort. While a complete ban on animal testing may represent the long-term goal, the legislature has not provided a timeline or specified the precise conditions required for its implementation. The current allowance for animal testing reflects a deliberate balancing of competing public interests—most notably, apart from animal welfare, public health and, to a lesser extent, the well-functioning of the internal market.

This trade-off helps to explain the variations across legislative instruments and sectors regarding the extent to which animal testing is still permitted. Where the public health interest carries less weight—as in the case of cosmetic products—there is correspondingly less room for animal testing. This naturally results in divergences across different legislative regimes. Here again, the Court of Justice has played a role in addressing ambiguities and inconsistencies. In its judgment on the scope of the animal testing ban under the Cosmetics Regulation, the Court clarified that no hierarchy exists between different legislative acts. General legislation such as REACH does not take precedence over sector-specific rules, and stricter provisions (on animal testing) do not override more permissive ones by default. The Court held that the ban on animal testing under the Cosmetics Regulation applies only to tests assessing effects on end users, thus delineating the scope of the prohibition.¹¹⁰

Furthermore, the possibility of conducting animal tests remains embedded in the legislative framework precisely because of the trade-offs involved. Indeed, recent changes in legislation show that developments can both restrict and expand animal testing.¹¹¹ On the one hand, the Directive on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes has been amended to require the application of NAMs “wherever possible,” replacing the previous, more flexible standard of “where reasonably and practically available.” On the other hand, the increasing recognition of endocrine disruption as a serious public health risk has led to additional regulatory pressure—potentially resulting in more animal testing rather than less.

This presents a sobering reality for the future of animal-free testing. The barriers to progress are not merely technical, practical, or cultural in nature. Nor are they solely the result of ineffective or poorly designed legislation. Rather, they stem from the fundamental structure of the legislative framework itself, which simultaneously prioritizes animal welfare and mandates the protection of public health and the internal market. The most effective strategies, therefore, will be those that *seek to align* the public health interest with the goal of reducing and ultimately eliminating animal testing.

¹¹⁰ Case T-655/20 *Symrise*, ECLI:EU:T:2023:736.

¹¹¹ K. Stoykova, ‘Towards Non-Animal Testing in European Regulatory Toxicology: An Introduction to the REACH Framework and Challenges in Implementing the 3Rs’, *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2025, p. 6.